

Phytochemical Investigation of *Anamirta cocculus* Linn.

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Anamirta cocculus Linn.¹ (family : Menispermaceae) is found in humid regions of India. Earlier investigation on the seeds of this plant reported¹ picrotoxin as the active principle. Herein we report the isolation of stearic acid in seeds and fumaric acid in flowers of the plant.

The alcoholic extract of the air-dried leaves of *A. cocculus* (800 g) on removal of the solvent yielded a solid residue (29 g), which was dissolved in minimum quantity of methanol. It was then adsorbed on SiO₂ gel and chromatographed over silica gel column eluting with solvents of increasing polarity. The eluates from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) was evaporated to a residue, which on crystallisation from methanol furnished colourless granules (2 g), m.p. 68–69° (lit.² 69°); *R_f* 0.83 (benzene-methanol, 20 : 0.5); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 740, 1 690, 1 460 and 1 300 cm⁻¹; δ (90 MHz; CDCl₃) 0.90 (CH₃), 1.30 (14 × CH₂), 1.62 (CH₂), 2.35 (CH₂); *m/z* (rel. int. %) 285 (*M*+1) 284 (*M*+17.6), 267 (2), 255 (2), 241 (15), 227 (4), 213 (4), 198 (6), 184 (14), 160 (8), 156 (8), 142 (10), 137 (35). Ir, ¹H nmr, mass spectral data and m.m.p. of the granules were identical with those reported for stearic acid².

Similarly, the methanolic extract of dried flowers of *A. cocculus* (300 g) yielded a semi-solid (17 g) after removal

of the solvent. The semi-solid was then dissolved in minimum quantity of methanol, adsorbed on silica gel, subjected to column chromatography over silica gel column and eluted with solvents of increasing polarity. The benzene-chloroform (9 : 1) eluate gave a solid which was crystallised from methanol as colourless fine needles, m.p. 289–90° (lit.³ 290°); positive bromothymol blue test for acids; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2 700, 1 680, 1 590 and 1 450 cm⁻¹; δ (90 MHz; CD₃OCD₃) 6.82 (2H, s); *m/z* (rel. int. %) 116.0108 (8.75 C₄H₄O₄), 99 (13.9), 88 (11.6), 72 (4), 71 (5), 55 (7), 45 (9), 44 (9). Ir, ¹H nmr, mass and m.m.p. data were identical with those reported for fumaric acid³.

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References

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